

QUALITY OF IRRIGATION WATER. EFFECT ON p_H VALUE AND EXCHANGEABLE BASES OF SOILS

By A. G. ASGHAR AND C. L. DHAWAN.

Irrigation water containing sodium salts even within permissible limits would produce a slow deterioration on good soil.

A negative salt index of a water sample is a useful and safe indication of its suitability for irrigation purposes. The waters with positive salt indices would produce slow deterioration in the soil, while waters with negative salt indices may even be used for reclamation purposes.

Sodium salts in the irrigation water increase the p_H value and the exchangeable sodium and potassium of the soil. A corresponding decrease in the exchangeable calcium is also brought about with the consequent lowering of the fertility of the soil.

Treatment of bad irrigation waters can be effected by the addition of gypsum or calcium permullite.

The p_H value and the total salt contents of a soil are the two important factors which must be carefully controlled in soil treatment. Taylor (*Indian Farming*, 1940, 1, 424) has laid down limits of fertility and deterioration of soils in relation to their p_H and total salt content. The conclusion drawn from this study is that if the salt content of the soil exceeds 0.2% or the alkalinity exceeds p_H value of 8.5, then soil deterioration has commenced and the crop yields will be below the normal. In addition to these factors, exchangeable bases have also been considered to be an index of fertility.

There are two points to be considered in this connection. When saline water is used for irrigation purpose, salts are added to the soil. Even if the salt concentration is very low and a part of the salt is removed by plants, there is likely to be a gradual accumulation of salts, which may produce 'Thur' in the long run, and ultimately the soil may become alkaline and reach the final stage of deterioration. The second point is the immediate effect of salts on plant growth, as all the plants cannot resist the effect of salts to the same extent.

Kelly (*Trans. Amer. Soc. Civ. Eng.*, 1941, Vol. 106) has mentioned the pioneer work of Hilgard, Forbes, and Schofield; but he has not laid down limits of suitability of irrigation waters. Puffles (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, 47, 447) while studying the effect of saline water on loess soils has concluded that a saline water possessing a high concentration of sodium salts, as compared with calcium salts, would eventually turn the soil useless for agricultural purposes. Taylor, Puri and Asghar (Memoir, Punjab Irrigation Research, 1935, Vol. IV, No 9) have expressed the following empirical formula for specifying the quality of an irrigation water. All quantities in this formula refer to parts per hundred thousand.

$$\text{Salt index} = (\text{Total Na} - 24.5) - (\text{total Ca} - \text{Ca in CaCO}_3 \times 4.85).$$

The salt index is negative for all good waters and positive for those unsuitable for irrigation purposes. They have not put forward any experimental evidence in support of their empirical formula. It was therefore felt necessary to determine the limits

of suitability of the commonly present salts in the irrigation water. The object of this investigation is to study in detail the chemical behaviour of the various salines usually present in the irrigation waters, their ultimate effect upon the soil, and rendering the unsuitable waters fit for irrigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

(i). Experiments were carried out to study the nature of the reactions taking place during the use of water containing different salts for irrigation.

Seven circular plots of land of 16" diameter were enclosed by galvanised iron sheets up to a depth of 1'-3". About 4" of galvanised iron sheet were kept above the natural surface for the facility of irrigation. One inch irrigation at a time, with sodium carbonate solution of strengths varying from 10 parts to 60 parts per 100 litres, was given daily. The losses due to evaporation during the experiments were not determined. One plot was irrigated with tap water which contained 15 parts per 100,000 of salts and this served as a control. Soil samples were taken after 17 and 32 inches of irrigation. Initial and final p_H value, initial and final exchangeable calcium and sodium plus potassium were determined.

The methods used for these determinations were:—

1. p_H value by glass electrode (of 1 : 5 soil-water suspension).
2. Exchangeable calcium by Puri's method (Puri, *Soil Sci.*, 1935, **40**, 383).
3. Exchangeable sodium and potassium by Puri's method (Puri, *ibid.*, 1935, **40**, 249).
4. Degree of alkalisation (D. A.) *i.e.*, the ratio of the amount of exchangeable monovalent bases (Na + K) in the soil to the maximum amount of monovalent ion the soil is capable of binding by exhaustive treatment with a neutral salt, the soils being alkaline; the latter has been taken to be equivalent to the sum of the major bases present in the exchange complex *e.g.* Na + K + Ca + Mg.

$$D. A. = \frac{Ex (Na + K)}{Ex (Na + K + Ca + Mg)} \times 100.$$

The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of sodium carbonate solution on soil constants.

Serial No.	Salt conc.*	Degree of alkalisation						Total salts percentage		
		p_H		After irrigation of			After irrigation of			
		Initial.	17".	32".	Initial.	17".	32".	Initial.	17".	32".
1	0.00	8.28	8.25	8.45	8.7	8.2	10.4	0.10	0.10	0.11
2	10.0	8.00	8.18	8.42	8.1	13.3	14.2	0.12	0.11	0.12
3	20.0	7.85	8.38	8.60	5.6	13.4	20.0	0.08	0.10	0.11
4	30.0	8.50	8.75	9.40	10.1	20.3	25.5	0.11	0.12	0.12
5	40.0	8.31	8.70	9.10	2.8	21.5	20.9	0.06	0.08	0.10
6	50.0	7.85	8.80	8.90	5.5	30.6	35.5	0.08	0.09	0.08
7	60.0	8.27	8.85	9.20	5.2	23.7	27.3	0.08	0.12	0.13

* In parts per 100,000.

The results show that tap water has no effect on the p_H value or the degree of alkalisiation of the soil, while in all the other cases there is a definite increase in the p_H value, which is more marked with high concentrations of sodium carbonate. There is an increase in the degree of alkalisiation proportionate to the salt concentration.

The results further indicate that even if the irrigation water has sodium carbonate concentrations below 60 parts per 100 litres, deterioration of the soil might result. Hence irrigation waters, which might appear good for crop cultivation in the beginning for a certain soil and a particular crop, might have a lasting ill effect on the soil.

It was also observed that when the sodium carbonate solution was added to the plots, it took some time to disappear from the soil surface. The solution (20 c. c.) was pipetted out and titrated for carbonate and bicarbonate. The results are given in Table II. If the carbonate solution was not converted into bicarbonate, it would have considerably affected the p_H value and the exchangeable bases of the soil.

TABLE II
Conversion of Na_2CO_3 into NaHCO_3 .

Temp. = 23°

Na_2CO_3 conc. (parts per 100,000)	% Na_2CO_3 converted into NaHCO_3	
	1.5 hours.	2.0 hours.
10.0	50.0	50.0
20.0	37.5	35.0
30.0	41.5	41.7
40.0	25.0	31.3
50.0	20.0	25.0
60.0	20.8	29.2

(ii). In order to determine the effect of other salts in irrigation waters on the soil constants, a different procedure was adopted which is described below.

A typical Punjab soil (50 g.) was taken in a Buchner funnel and leached with solutions of increasing strengths of sodium chloride, sodium sulphate and sodium bicarbonate in 100 c. c. lots. After passing 4000 c. c. which is equivalent to (about 40 inches of irrigation) the soils were dried and examined for p_H and exchangeable bases. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III
Effect of NaCl , Na_2SO_4 and NaHCO_3 solution on soil constants.

Salt (parts per 100,000).	(a) Effect of NaCl .			(b) Effect of Na_2SO_4 .			(c) Effect of NaHCO_3 .		
	p_H .	Degree of alkalisiation.	Total p_H . salts.	Degree of alkalisiation	Total p_H . salts.	Degree of alkalisiation	Total salts.		
0.0	7.50	4.10	0.130%	7.50	4.10	0.13%	7.5	4.10	0.13%
10.0	8.05	12.7	0.14	8.0	10.8	0.14	8.3	22.0	0.17
20.0	8.15	13.7	0.14	7.9	11.5	0.14	8.55	28.7	0.21
30.0	8.10	15.1	0.15	8.4	20.3	0.16	8.80	45.8	0.25
40.0	8.10	16.7	0.15	8.3	17.6	0.15	9.35	69.5	0.27
50.0	8.25	18.4	0.15	8.3	24.0	0.17	9.65	80.3	0.31
60.0	8.30	19.2	0.15	8.5	26.5	0.17	9.88	84.0	0.35

It will be seen that there is a gradual increase in the p_n value and in the degree of alkalisiation, although the salt concentrations taken are all within the permissible limits of 60 parts per 100,000. These results clearly indicate that prolonged irrigation with such waters would produce slow deterioration of the soil, sodium bicarbonate being the most deleterious. There is a marked increase in the total salt content of soils treated with sodium-bicarbonate. Some of the sodium bicarbonate was left free in the soil, hence there was a marked increase in the total salts, and degree of alkalisiation.

(iii). Experiments were next undertaken to determine the effect of irrigation waters having different salt indices on the soil. The same soil (25 g.) was taken in different Buchner funnels and leached with 2000 c.c. of water samples having different salt concentrations and salt indices. The p_n value, exchangeable calcium and exchangeable sodium plus potassium, before and after leaching, are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Effect of leaching on a typical Punjab soil with water samples of varying salt indices.

Sr. No	Salt index of waters.	Salts in parts per 100,000.	p_n .	Degree of alkalisiation.	Total salt.
1	Original soil	...	8.50	11.40	0.13%
2	- 2.35	81.2	8.00	9.1	0.10
3	-35.94	28.3	8.00	10.9	0.11
4	-73.51	54.5	7.97	4.4	0.10
5	-93.48	73.0	7.85	6.6	0.11
6	+ 5.20	95.0	9.30	23.5	0.15
7	+23.68	128.0	9.33	40.8	0.17
8	+31.96		9.90	42.0	0.18
9	+37.40	161.2	9.85	58.3	0.18
10	+38.01	165.5	9.48	46.7	0.17
11	+390.17	1212.9	9.32	50.3	0.22

The p_n value remains almost the same with water samples of negative salt indices, but waters having positive salt indices increase the p_n value to such an extent that the soil attains the deterioration limits.

Moreover, there is a definite decrease in the degree of alkalisiation with negative salt indices and its increase with positive salt indices. Hence, deterioration would be sure to result with waters having positive salt indices, while reclamation would be possible with waters of negative salt indices.

(iv). To study in greater detail the effect of water samples having positive salt indices, a special type of soil of high base exchange capacity (56 m.e.), high exchangeable calcium (54.1 m.e.) and high clay (58.9%) was used, as such a soil was expected to give a clearer indication of the effect of positive salt index on the exchangeable bases. The soil sample (25 g.) was leached in a Buchner funnel with 500 and 1000 c.c. of water in 100 c.c. lots. The results are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Effect of leaching with waters of positive salt indices of a black cotton soil.

Sr. No.	Salt index.	Total salts in parts per 100,000.	Vol. of leachate.	p _H .	Degree of alkalisation.	Total salts.
1	Original soil	...	...	8.00	4.1	0.06%
2	+ 22.71	130.7	500 c. c.	8.57	5.7	0.08
3	+ 22.7	130.7	1000	8.8	5.0	0.10
4	+ 31.98	176.3	500	8.22	6.2	0.10
5	+ 31.98	176.3	1000	8.30	9.0	0.11
6	+379.72	1152.3	500	8.15	25.5	0.16
7	+379.72	1152.3	1000	8.60	28.2	0.17
8	+391.07	1188.8	500	8.42	23.4	0.19
9	+391.07	1188.8	1000	8.40	26.6	0.20

The results show an increase in the p_H value in all the cases and that in some cases the soil even reaches the limits of deterioration.

There is a regular increase in the degree of alkalisation showing the deteriorating effect of positive salt index.

Thus the results point towards the deterioration of soils with waters of positive salt indices.

(v). Taylor, Puri and Asghar (*loc. cit.*) stated that all waters having 60 to 120 parts of total solids per 100 litres and having negative salt indices were suitable for irrigation purposes.

To verify this statement, leaching was carried out with water samples containing total solids varying from 32 parts to 103 parts. The results are presented in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Effect of leaching with waters of varying salt indices having total salts less than 120.

Sr. No.	Salt index.	Total salts in parts per 100,000.	Vol. of leachate.	p _H .	Degree of alkalisation.	Total salt.
1	Original soil	...	...	8.00	4.1	0.06%
2	-30.29	32.62	500 c.c.	8.25	...	0.07
3	-30.29	32.62	1000	8.30	...	0.07
4	-15.28	40.62	500	8.45	...	0.06
5	-15.28	40.62	1000	8.45	...	0.08
6	- 8.72	56.16	500	8.30	3.7	0.10
7	- 8.72	56.16	1000	8.35	5.5	0.08
8	-94.97	76.18	500	8.00	...	0.08
9	-94.97	76.18	1000	7.95	...	0.09
10	+ 0.36	84.13	500	8.42	4.2	0.10
11	+ 0.36	84.13	1000	8.52	4.3	0.11
12	+10.33	96.09	500	8.90	8.8	0.09
13	+10.33	96.09	1000	8.93	9.8	0.10
14	+11.91	103.26	500	8.50	9.9	0.11
15	+11.91	103.26	1000	8.80	9.7	0.10

This shows that, with negative salt indices, the degree of alkalisation reduces to zero, while with positive salt indices, although the total solids are within the permissible limits, there is a gradual increase in the degree of alkalisation.

Treatment of Waters Unsuitable for Irrigation

It is well known that waters unfit for irrigation can be improved by the addition of calcium salts. Four such samples of water were treated with calcium sulphate (5 g. to 1000 c. c.), the solution filtered to remove any excess of calcium sulphate and the filtrates analysed. The results of analysis before and after treatment are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Effect of calcium sulphate on the quality of water.

Water No.→ Salt contents.	1		2		3		4	
	Original.	After CaSO ₄ treatment.	Original.	After CaSO ₄ treatment.	Original.	After CaSO ₄ treatment.	Original.	After CaSO ₄ treatment.
	Parts per 100 litres.							
CaSO ₄	...	118.32	...	87.7	...	48.28	...	120.36
Ca(HCO ₃) ₂ as CaCO ₃	20.00	41.50	23.75	53.00	16.00	59.00	6.50	39.00
CaCl ₂	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
Na ₂ SO ₄	40.00	24.85	35.00	63.35	20.00	71.10	40.00	87.53
Na ₂ CO ₃	...	...	...	...	12.72	...	20.14	...
NaHCO ₃ as Na ₂ CO ₃	24.38	...	31.54	...	38.16	...	25.44	...
NaCl	29.84	29.84	32.76	32.76	11.70	11.70	11.70	11.70
Total	114.22	214.51	123.05	226.81	98.58	190.18	103.78	258.59
p _H	8.85	7.75	7.95	7.40	8.20	7.18	8.55	7.40
Salt index	+10.76	-173.46	-13.39	-66.94	+8.65	-71.48	+12.83	-163.21

The decrease in p_H was well marked and the salt index changed from a positive to a large negative value, in all the cases showing that waters were rendered harmless.

Another substance which might be used for treatment of such waters is calcium permutite. Five hundred c. c. of water were treated with 5 g. of calcium permutite and kept for about 3 hours. These were filtered and the filtrate analysed. The results are given in Table VIII, and show a marked decrease in total solids.

TABLE VIII

Effect of calcium permutite on the quality of water

Sr. No.	Total salts in parts per 100,000.		Salt index	
	Original.	After treatment.	Original.	After treatment.
1	103.16	89.10	+12.92	+1.50
2	124.41	82.38	+23.70	+2.97
3	123.76	87.91	+14.09	-60.99
4	90.23	58.04	+7.93	-24.16

The high positive index either changes to a negative one or decreases in magnitude. Calcium permutite is therefore another suitable substance for treatment of such waters.